

Infrared Spectra of Natural and Microbially Synthesised Humic Acids

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Humic acid has been extracted from alluvial soil, West Bengal. Microbial humic acid has been produced by the treatment of fungus species, streptomyces spc7. IR spectra of these two products along with the Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} complexes of the natural one are presented here.

PREVIOUS studies on electrometric titrations and absorption spectroscopy^{1,2} have revealed the nature of metallo-organic interactions of soil. Further information is sought to be obtained using infrared spectroscopy as has been done by others^{3,4,5}.

In the present study an attempt has been made to get some structural information on humic acids, natural as well as synthetic (microbial), and the nature of their interaction with trivalent metal ions, viz., Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , with the help of IR spectroscopy.

Experimental

Methods and Materials :

Humic acid used in this investigation has been extracted from Chinsura soil, West Bengal by the standard procedure as stated earlier^{1,6}. For microbial humic acid production, the fungus species, streptomyces spc7, has been used. This culture was grown in a base medium of 30 g dextrose, 0.1 g

The flasks were generally incubated on the flat side for 5 weeks at 22°.

The cultures were then filtered and the filtrate was concentrated to approximately 50% of volume at 60°. The liquid was again filtered and then dialysed against frequent changes of distilled water for 48 hr. The humic acid was precipitated by adjusting the pH of the solution to 2.0 with HCl or H_3PO_4 . This humic acid was then dried at 60°.

Results and Discussions

Fig. 1 shows that the infrared spectra of the soil humic acid used in this investigation are nearly identical with those reported by earlier workers^{4,5}. From the tentative assignments (Table 1) it may be said that natural humic acid has an aromatic ring structure with hydroxyl group in the form of polymeric association bonded with secondary amino group and hydrogen bonded H_2O molecule⁷. This observation is in good agreement with that of Haworth⁸.

yeast extract, 2.0 g of K_2HPO_4 , 0.25 g KCl, 0.5 g $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ and 7.5 g asparagine in 1 litre tap water. The dextrose was sterilised separately and added to 150 ml portions of sterile medium in 1 litre prescription bottles. One ml of suspensions of 5-day culture of the fungus was added to each flask.

On comparison of results of natural humic acid and the corresponding Fe- and Al-complexes, the following points are noticeable :

- (a) existence of the peak at 3448 cm^{-1} in all these three cases;

TABLE I. INFRARED SPECTRA OF HUMIC ACID NATURAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL AND OF THE Fe/Al COMPLEXES OF THE NATURAL ONE

Humic Acid (Natural)	Frequency in cm^{-1} of		Humic Acid (Microbiological)	Tentative Assignments
	Ha-Fe Complex	Ha-Al Complex		
3448 (Sp,St)	3448 (Sp,St)	3448 (Sp,St)	3333 (Sp,St)	Due to presence of NH, OH or H-bonded H_2O
2899 (Sp,w)	—	—	2899 (Sp,m)	Due to combination of OH and CH stretching of COOH group.
—	2315 (Sh,w)	2315 (Sh,w)	2326 (Sp,w)	Due to presence of zwitter ions of $> \text{NH}^+$ and $\cdot \text{NH}_2^+$ etc.
1653 (Sp,m)	—	—	1653 (Sp,St)	Due to $-\text{CO}$ stretching
—	1558 (Sp,m)	1600 (Sp,m)	—	Due to antisymmetrical stretching of free carboxylate ion (CO_2^-).
—	—	—	1538 (Sh,w)	Due to aromatic ring
—	—	—	1453 (Sh,w)	Due to C-H deformation
1399 (Sh,St)	—	—	1390 (Sp,w)	Due to OH bonding
—	1408 (b,St)	1370 (b,m)	—	Due to symmetrical stretching of free carboxylate ion (CO_2^-).
—	—	—	1235 (b,w)	Due to $-\text{CO}$ stretching
—	—	—	1075 (b,m)	Due to $-\text{CO}$ stretching

N.B.—Sp = Sharp; Sh = Short; b = Broad; St = Strong; m = medium; w = Weak.

- (b) the peak at 2899 cm^{-1} found in natural humic acid has disappeared in its Fe- and Al-complexes but there appears one in the region of 2315 cm^{-1} ; and
- (c) shifting of the peak (i) at 1653 cm^{-1} found in natural humic acid to 1558 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} in Fe- and Al-complexes respectively and (ii) at 1399 cm^{-1} in natural humic acid to 1408 cm^{-1} and 1370 cm^{-1} in Fe- and Al-complexes respectively.

The observation mentioned in (a) may be due to the fact that the carboxyl group present in humic acid undergoes interaction with metal ions during complex formation to form metal-carboxylate band. Besides this, from the characteristics as mentioned in (b) and (c) above, it may be inferred that both Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} have formed complexes with humic acid bonding through carboxylic oxygen. The peaks at 1558 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} in Fe- and Al-complexes respectively may be assigned to be due to anti-symmetrical stretching of free carboxylate ion and similarly those at 1408 cm^{-1} and 1370 cm^{-1} due to symmetrical stretching of free carboxylate ion. According to Nakamoto⁷, separation between anti-symmetrical and symmetrical stretching vibrations as compared to the free CO_2^- anion depend upon metal oxygen bonding type. When the separation between two bands is greater, presence of bond of

the type, $\begin{array}{c} \diagup \\ \text{O}-\text{M} \\ \text{C}=\text{O} \end{array}$ is indicated. The decrease in separation is comparable with equivalence of the bonding of the two carboxyl oxygens of the type $\begin{array}{c} \diagup \\ \text{O}-\text{M} \\ \text{C}=\text{O} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{M}$ supporting intermolecular attraction. Based on this view, from the measurement of separation between the antisymmetrical and symmetrical

stretching vibrations in case of Fe- and Al-complexes it is found that separation is less in case of the Fe-complex than that in the Al-complex. From this relative decrease it may be inferred that both Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} form complexes by bonding through carboxylic oxygen and the probability of having the nature of bonding of the type $\begin{array}{c} \diagup \\ \text{O}-\text{M} \\ \text{C}=\text{O} \end{array} \rightarrow \text{M}$ is greater in case of the Fe-complex than in the case of the Al-complex.

It has already been established that Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} form complexes with humic acid by bonding through hydroxy, amino and carboxylic acid groups⁹. Therefore, it is expected that the peak at 3448 cm^{-1} found in natural humic acid should have undergone some change in its corresponding complexes. But the fact that it still exists as such in its complexes may be attributed to the presence of a large number of such groups of which only a limited number is taken up by the metal ions, the others remaining free and thus causing the peak to appear in the same region even after complexation. The exact extent to which this interaction has taken place cannot, however, be ascertained on the basis of the above special measurements.

From IR spectra of microbial humic acid, it may be said that this humic acid is more or less identical in structure to natural humic acid although some new peaks are detected in the former (cf. table). This discrepancy may be assigned to the lower molecular weight (450) and hence less polymeric character of the microbial humic acid¹⁰ in comparison to the natural one (mol. wt. 2040). Besides these common peaks, the extra one at 2326 cm^{-1} in the microbial product may be due to presence of zwitter ions of the types, $> \text{NH}^+$, NH_2^+ etc. in this species.

References

1. M. ADHIKARI and G. C. HAZRA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1970, **33**, 5.
2. M. SCHNITZER and S. I. M. SKINNER. *Soil Sci.*, 1963, **96**, 86.
3. I. KEGAYA, KENJINO (Chagyo Gijutsu Kenkyu, 1969, No. 37, 39).
4. J. F. DORMAAR, *Canad. J. Soil Sci.*, 1970, **50**, 89.
5. F. E. BEAR, *Chemistry of Soils*, Renhold Publ. Corp., New York, 1968.
6. K. NAKAMOTO, *Infrared spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds*. Wiley and Sons, New York, 1963.
7. R. D. HAWORTH, *Soil Sci.*, 1971, **111**, 71.
8. G. CHAKRABARTI, D.Phil. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1972.
9. M. SCHNITZER and J. G. DESJARDIN, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1962, **26**, 362.